

Multiple Diseases Prediction From Blood Sample Using Random Forest

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Abstract— In this study, we focus solely on the prediction of diseases that may be detected using a wide range of blood factors, such as heart disease, liver disease, and anaemia. We hope to identify the method with the highest accuracy in disease prediction by conducting a rigorous comparative analysis of various binary classifier techniques, such as Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest Classifier, and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN). By using a data-driven approach, we highlight the critical importance of blood parameters as powerful indicators of illness risk, allowing for early detection. This technique not only demonstrates the potential of machine learning in healthcare, but also the benefits of using blood parameters as the major source of information for disease prediction, which promises to improve healthcare service accuracy.

Keywords—Disease prediction, Logistic Regression, Random Forest, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Support Vector Machine (SVM)

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, machine learning has significantly advanced and found applications in a wide range of domains, particularly in healthcare. The use of machine learning models has the potential to revolutionize medical diagnostics and enhance patient outcomes by simultaneously predicting multiple diseases.

Predictive modelling empowers medical professionals to anticipate patient outcomes and disease trends, enabling timely interventions and personalized treatment strategies. This research focuses on the prediction of three major medical conditions: heart disease, anaemia, and liver disease. These conditions pose significant challenges to global healthcare systems and individuals due to their diverse etiologies and health implications.

Heart disease encompasses a variety of cardiovascular conditions affecting the heart and blood vessels. Risk factors for heart disease include high blood pressure, high cholesterol, and certain lifestyle choices.

Anaemia is characterized by a low red blood cell count or insufficient haemoglobin levels and can result from a range of factors, such as genetic predisposition, chronic illnesses, and inadequate nutrition.

Liver disease is a broad category of disorders that impair the liver's functionality. These conditions are often triggered by viral infections, excessive alcohol consumption, fatty liver

disease, or genetic factors, and they carry substantial health risks.

Blood parameters, such as haemoglobin levels, cholesterol, and other blood-related markers, play a pivotal role in understanding and diagnosing these medical conditions. The primary algorithm employed for disease classification in this study is the Random Forest Classifier. This choice is based on its demonstrated ability to navigate complex medical data, consistently achieve high predictive accuracy, and seamlessly adapt to diverse feature sets and datasets.

Random Forest

Random Forest is a robust ensemble learning algorithm widely used in machine learning. It combines multiple decision trees trained on random subsets of the data and features to deliver highly accurate predictions in both classification and regression tasks. It excels at handling complex datasets, is less prone to overfitting, and provides insights into feature importance. Its versatility and reliability have made it a popular choice in various domains, contributing to its reputation as a powerful and effective machine learning tool.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

With the potential to transform disease prediction and enhance patient care, machine learning is a promising tool in the healthcare industry. The idea of incorporating machine learning models into healthcare for early diagnosis and improved medical outcomes excites researchers and practitioners. This review outlines the key developments in the field of machine learning for disease prediction, which has been the subject of numerous studies.

Heart Disease Prediction: One of the leading causes of death globally, heart disease presents a significant public health issue. Research studies have employed a variety of datasets and methodologies, suggesting the potential of machine learning to tackle the intricate issues surrounding the diagnosis and treatment of heart disease. The results of this study [1] demonstrate the effectiveness of machine learning in enhancing the diagnosis of heart disease, with accuracy levels attained that either surpass or correspond with those of earlier investigations. The highest accuracy of 88.5% obtained using KNN and Logistic Regression surpasses or is comparable to the accuracy noted in earlier research.

Anaemia Disease Prediction: Six classification algorithms (Linear Support Vector Machine, Random Forest, Decision Tree, Gaussian Naive Bayes, Stacking Classifier, and Voting Classifier) for the detection of anaemia were investigated in a thorough study [2]. The models that predicted anaemia with the highest accuracy were the Voting Classifier, Decision Tree, and Random Forest, which bodes well for more precise and effective diagnosis.

Liver Disease Prediction: The liver is a vital organ that plays a role in metabolism, detoxification, and the production of essential proteins. Because liver diseases can frequently be asymptomatic in their early stages, early detection is essential.

According to the results of study [3], SVM and logistic regression were both investigated as machine learning models for predicting the likelihood of liver disorders. The study does note, though, that SVM outperformed Logistic Regression in terms of predicting the likelihood of liver disorders.

An additional investigation [4] examined the potential applications of machine learning, specifically the Support Vector Machines (SVM) model, in the prediction of heart disease, diabetes, and Parkinson's disease. The outcomes showed an amazing 98.3% accuracy, highlighting the potential of SVM in building a framework for multi-disease prediction.

III. MOTIVATION

The goal of this study is to fill a vacuum in disease prediction by simultaneously considering anaemia, heart disease, and liver disease based on blood characteristics. These illnesses were chosen for their clinical importance and potential for life-threatening complications. The importance is in providing a more complete picture of a patient's health, expediting diagnoses, and enabling early intervention, all of which are critical for improving patient outcomes. Early prediction is critical because it can lead to prompt medical attention, preventive actions, and more efficient use of healthcare resources, ultimately improving healthcare access and patient well-being.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The methods and procedures used to develop prediction models for three distinct diseases—liver disease, heart disease, and anemia—are described in this study. Developing precise machine learning models that can determine whether a person has any of these diseases is the main goal of this research.

Fig1:Flowchart for disease prediction

A. Data Collection and Preprocessing

Relevant datasets are gathered for every one of the three illnesses. To ensure the quality of the data, these datasets are thoroughly inspected. To ensure that no information is lost, missing values in the data are handled by the SimpleImputer using a "mean" strategy.

```

# Impute missing values
imputer = SimpleImputer(strategy='mean')
X_train_imputed = imputer.fit_transform(X_train)
X_test_imputed = imputer.transform(X_test)
    
```

Fig2 :Improving data quality

B. Data Splitting

The data is split into training and testing datasets for each disease. This separation facilitates model training and evaluation.

C. Feature Engineering and Scaling

Features for Disease Prediction

Heart Disease:

- a. Age, Sex, Chest pain,
- b. Blood pressure, Cholesterol
- c. Fasting blood sugar, ECG results
- d. Max heart rate, Exercise-induced angina
- e. ST depression, Exercise ST slope
- f. Vessels,
- g. Thalassemia
- h. Target variable (presence/absence of heart disease)

Anemia:

- a. Sex
- b. Haemoglobin
- c. MCH, MCHC, MCV
- d. Target variable (presence/absence of anemia)

Liver Disease:

- a. Age, Sex
- b. Bilirubin
- c. Alkaline Phosphatase
- d. ALT, AST, Total Proteins
- e. Albumin, A/G Ratio
- f. Target variable (presence/absence of liver disease)

D. Model Selection and Training

For every disease dataset, several machine learning algorithms are taken into consideration, such as Random Forest, Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machine (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Decision Trees.

E. Model Evaluation

Model performance is assessed using metrics such as accuracy, classification reports, confusion matrices. The best-performing model for each disease is determined based on accuracy.

Model for heart disease:

Fig 3: Model comparison of heart disease dataset

For every disease dataset, several machine learning algorithms are taken into consideration, such as Random Forest, Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machine (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Decision Trees.

Model for anaemia:

Fig 4: Model comparison of anaemia disease dataset

We selected the Random Forest algorithm as our model of choice for anemia prediction due to its remarkable accuracy and robust performance, as evidenced by comparative experiments.

Model for Liver Disease:

Fig 5: Model comparison of liver disease dataset

In our research, both Random Forest and Logistic Regression models achieved similar accuracy levels. However, a more detailed analysis revealed that Random Forest, while equally accurate, exhibited higher model complexity and greater robustness to noise, making it a more favorable choice for applications where intricate relationships and data noise are critical factors.

F. Model Deployment

The trained models for heart disease, anemia, and liver disease are saved using joblib for future use in diagnosing these conditions.

```
import joblib
joblib.dump(rf_classifier, 'anemiamodel.pkl')
```

Fig 6: Saving model

G. User Input and Prediction

A user interface is created to accept input data, including gender, relevant blood parameters, and patient information. The user input data is fed into the best-performing model for each disease. The model provides predictions regarding the

presence or absence of the respective disease based on the user's input.

H. Interpretation of Predictions

The research culminates in offering interpretable predictions for each disease, which can guide healthcare professionals and patients in making informed decisions regarding early diagnosis and intervention.

V. RESULT

When the code receives input from the user, it processes the information and predicts whether the individual is at risk for liver, heart, or anemia problems.

Fig 7: User interface for multiple disease prediction

A Random Forest Classifier is used to make predictions on three different datasets.

The prediction's accuracy on the testing data was as follows:
 100% for anemia
 75.21% for liver disease
 84% for heart disease

Various performance indicators were also calculated to assess the accuracy of the forecasts, including:

F1 score:
 100% for anemia
 83.80% for liver disease
 84% for heart disease

Precision:
 100% for anemia
 81.52% for liver disease
 84% for heart disease

VI. CONCLUSION

We conducted a detailed investigation of illness prediction using machine learning approaches in this study, concentrating on three key health conditions: heart disease, anaemia, and liver disease. The major purpose is to predict whether a person has any of the diseases mentioned using the best accurate prediction approach among multiple binary classifiers, such as Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machines (SVM), Random Forest Classifier, and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN).

The study's findings demonstrate the potential of machine learning in healthcare, with a flawless 100% accuracy for anaemia and strong performance with 75.21% accuracy for liver disease and 84% accuracy for heart disease. These findings highlight the importance of data-driven healthcare in supporting prompt interventions and individualized therapies, while also emphasizing the need for additional study to improve predictions across a range of health conditions.

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